

WORK FROM HOME IN INDIAN WORK SCENARIO

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Abstract:

The outbreak of the novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) and the subsequent work-from-home imperatives and lockdowns have led to significant economic disruptions around the world.

To curb the spread of COVID-19, the Government of India has imposed a lockdown since 25th March 2020. This has left the businesses with no choice but to work from home and ensure that the economic activities continue to move.

Currently, as India is facing a sudden surge, India Inc is playing it safe by extending work from home (WFH) for employees. Before the pandemic struck, what seemed like an incredible perk for many employees has now been fretted about.

The impact of this paradigm shift and mitigation strategies from offline to online work has become crucial and critical, so a study on the same has become imperative.

A primary and secondary study is conducted to better understand the implications of the current imperative to work from home, including readiness of employees across different sectors and occupations, we tried to gain insight into impact and the suitability, vulnerability of employees and employers in work from home scenario in India. It also tries to comprehend the employers and employees perspective on realization of productivity, teamwork, and communication.

Introduction

Work From home (WFH) is a concept where the employee can do his or her job from home. Work from home gives flexible working hours to the employee as well as the job for the employer is done with ease. Work from home is helpful to delivering work life balance to the employee, and also parallelly helps the company to get the work done. Nowadays, most of the employers are offering this option to their employees.

Work from home (or working from home) is a modern work approach enabled through internet and mobility wherein irrespective of the physical location of an individual work can be done. Work from Home is also known as Working remotely or telecommuting which implies that the employee is working from a remote location usually home.

Technology in today's world is easing the work process for most of the employees and business owners. Technology is bridging the gap between distant employees and organizations, improving the performances along with generating more sales.

In today's time, most of the office software could be easily installed on a home PC, allowing employees to work and communicate in the same manner as done in the workplace via emails, chats, and video messaging services like Skype.

Advantages of Work from Home

There are many advantages while working from home.

1. There is more job applicant for a particular job with certain people with location constraint or disabled people can apply for the job. Even parents with children who tend to leave job can be retained for the job.

2. There is more work life balance. Many people claim that a more quieter or friendly atmosphere is found at home which helps to concentrate on the work as well as they can complete the assigned work quickly.
3. There is a lot of savings with respect to cost of office infrastructure like spaces, electricity bills etc.
4. Employees feel motivated as they get a good work life balance, and improves their productivity

Disadvantages of Work from Home

There are many disadvantages as well

1. There is always a major problem with monitoring the work.
2. The cost of technological infrastructure that is required for implementing the concept.
3. There is always a security problem with data being transferred and that can't be monitored easily.
4. All jobs doesn't is not suitable for work from home concept. Sometimes communication problem between employees makes it problematic for a job.

Objectives

- To study the impact of work from home on Employees
- To study the impact of work from home on Employers.
- To understand the work life balance during work from home.

Research methodology

1. Primary data
 - Collection data through Google form
2. Secondary data
 - Website
 - Wikipedia
 - Newspapers
 - Magazines
3. Sample Size – 170

4. Sample Age – 18-50 years of Age

4. Sampling Area – Thane, Mumbai Suburbs, Mumbai City.

Findings

1.

Have you faced any pay cut during Pandemic?
173 responses

2.

Do you have a healthy work life balance while working from home?
173 responses

3.

Is communication with Employers, a challenge while working from home?
173 responses

4.

Do you have a healthy work life balance while working from home?
173 responses

5.

Would you prefer working from home even after Pandemic situation?
173 responses

6.

Do you feel your organisation is providing adequate support for Work From Home?
173 responses

7.

How do you feel about work from home concept?
173 responses

Suggestions:

- Keep employees engaged with recognition
- Equip your team with tech and productivity tools.
- Provide emotional and steady support.
- Establish daily check-ins
- Encourage dedicated workspaces
- Don't forget about non-work interactions and team building.

Limitations of the Research:

- Issues with sample and selection
- Insufficient sample size for statistical measurement
- Limited access to data
- Time constraints
- Time consuming
- No personal interaction with the respondents due to Covid measures

Conclusion:

1. The outbreak of the novel coronavirus (COVID-19) and the subsequent work-from-home imperatives and lockdowns have led to significant economic disruptions around the world.
2. The insights from prior studies on the impact of work from home arrangements do not extend to the current context since these arrangements were mostly limited to a select group of workers and/or organizations and were often self-selected.
3. However, what is interesting is that certain occupations, although characterized by high human proximity and low suitability to work from home, may well be amenable to this shift through technological innovation and technology-enabled business models.
4. For example, teaching associate professionals is an occupation with low suitability to work from home. However, in the past few days, we have witnessed several ed-tech companies like Byju's and Coursera offer their content for free to students.

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5. This can likely lead to changes in consumer behavior and render learning and teaching more suitable to work from home than in the past

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